

Examining the influence of attitude toward work on the organizational commitment

Eldefonso B. Natividad, PhD: Education Program Supervisor, Schools Division of the City of Batac.

Elita, B. Valdez, EdD: Professor, College of Education, Divine Word College of Vigan

Engr. Lloyd Mitchell S. Macadangang: Instructor, School of Nursing, Engineering, Architecture, Information and Technology, Divine Word College of Laoag.

Engr. Jayren R. Asuncion: Instructor, School of Nursing, Engineering, Architecture, Information and Technology, Divine Word College of Laoag.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received April 01, 2024

Received in rev. form. May 1, 2024

Accepted: May 13, 2024

Keywords: *attitude, affective, cognitive, commitment, continuance, normative.*

ABSTRACT

The study sought to investigate how employees' attitudes toward their work influence their commitment to the organization. To provide a comprehensive understanding, the researchers reviewed relevant literature. Employing a descriptive assessment and correlational research design, the study focused on the institution's employees as its population.

Data collection utilized validated research questionnaires tailored to the study's objectives. Results revealed a notable level of alignment between employees' attitudes toward work and their organizational commitment. Specifically, the correlation analysis highlighted significant associations between attitudes toward work and both affective and continuance commitment. However, no significant correlation was found between attitudes toward work and normative organizational commitment.

© 2024 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This open-access article is distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

JEL Classification: M15

Introduction

Businesses vie for distinction in a competitive landscape by cultivating a competitive workforce. While upskilling is crucial, fostering positive work behaviors is equally vital (Lee et al., 2016; Idrees et al., 2022; Youssef & Luthans, 2007; Cascio, 2006).

Behavior stems from attitude, comprising cognitive, affective, and conative aspects (Ajzen, 1993; Myers, 2013; Perloff, 2013; Liska, 1974). Positive attitudes drive positive behavior, underscoring the importance of attitude management (Ortmeyer, 1949).

Despite its significance, attitude management often gets overlooked in organizational management (Cabrera & Estacio, 2022; Rahiman & Kodikal, 2017; Brayfield & Crockett, 1955). This neglect jeopardizes organizational performance (Stackhouse et al., 2022).

The study explored how employees' attitudes toward work shape their organizational commitment, bridging a research gap and furnishing actionable insights for management.

Sections include: introduction, literature review, methodology, data presentation, results and discussion, and conclusion.

Literature review

The literature review aims to gather insights from past research on the subject and establish the study's theories. By examining existing literature, the researcher can build a solid understanding of the topic and develop guiding theories. The review will be organized thematically according to the study's focus.

The concept of attitude and attitude toward work and its effect on work performance.

Attitude, as defined by Merriam-Webster and the Cambridge Dictionary, encompasses mental and emotional positions toward objects, people, or events. Allport (1935) underscored its centrality in social psychology, defining it as a set of beliefs, emotions, and behaviors shaped by experience. Titchener (1910) and Koffka (1935) emphasized its role in driving behavior, while Thurstone (1929) viewed it as a force behind actions.

Applied to work, attitude influences behavioral intentions and performance. Aries and Rizqi (2013) characterized it as workers' feelings, beliefs, and judgments toward the work environment. Önal (2015), cited by Akcay et al. (2016), viewed it as tendencies shaped by work evaluations. Aligning with Ajzen (1993), Myers (2013), Perloff (2016), and Liska (1974), it encompasses cognitive, affective, and conative responses affecting behavior.

Research corroborates the link between attitude toward work and performance. Abun et al. (2021) found a correlation, while Abdalkrim and Elhalim (2016) observed impacts on job satisfaction. Akcay et al. (2016) similarly noted the influence of employees' work attitudes. Management interventions targeting attitude can enhance performance, satisfaction, and commitment (Borst et al., 2020). Addressing negative attitudes is crucial for performance improvement (Menon & Priyadarshini, 2018), as a positive attitude fosters employee performance (Almeida et al., 2012).

Organizational commitment

Commitment, whether to a cause, activity, or organization, encompasses dedication and loyalty. Leonard (2009) emphasizes its psychological dimension as a state of mind binding individuals to actions, echoed by Ajayi and Muraina (2016) and Ceylan (2020), who highlight emotional attachment and self-identification. Meyer and Allen (1991) and Porters et al. (1974) reinforce this view, linking commitment to decisions on organizational membership and identification with the organization. This psychological perspective is echoed by Idris and Manganaro (2017), Herrera and Heras-Rosas (2021), and Greenberg and Baron (2008).

Organizational commitment entails a psychological contract, posited by Rousseau (1995), reflecting reciprocal obligations and benefits in the employee-organization relationship. This contract influences employee behavior, delineated into relational and transactional dimensions (MacNeil, 1985). Relational contracts entail emotional exchange and loyalty based on expectations, while transactional contracts revolve around economic exchange.

Research by Fischer and Mansell (2009), Mathieu and Zajac (1990), Meyer et al. (2002), and Solinger et al. (2008) underscores the impact of organizational commitment on job satisfaction, involvement, and retention. Higher levels of commitment correlate with decreased turnover rates, reduced absenteeism, organizational citizenship behavior, and improved well-being (Angle & Perry, 1981; Mathieu & Zajac, 1990; Meyer et al., 2002; Solinger et al., 2008).

Dimensions of organizational commitment: affective, continuance and normative commitment.

Scholars agree that organizational commitment isn't simple; it is made up of several parts. Morrow (1993) broke it down into attitude and behavior. Attitude is about how someone feels about their job, like loyalty and attachment, while behavior is about what they do. This view aligns with Meyer, Allen, and Gellatly (1990), who see attitude as a positive judgment about the organization, reflecting in actions as Ajzen (1993) suggests. Best (1994) and Reicher (1985) add that commitment shows when people are dedicated to their tasks and the group they're part of within the organization. O'Reilly (1989) says commitment is shown through involvement, loyalty, and believing in the organization's values.

From this concept, scholars like Meyer and Allen (1997) proposed three dimensions: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Affective commitment is emotional attachment to the organization, which motivates employees to work harder (Johnson & Chang, 2006). Continuance commitment happens when someone believes staying is better than leaving because of costs and benefits (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Normative commitment is about feeling morally obligated to stay (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Muhammad et al., 2021).

O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) added three more dimensions: compliance, identification, and internalization. Compliance is when people work for rewards, like continuance commitment. Identification and internalization are about feeling connected to the organization, like affective commitment. Wechsler and Balfour (1996) also identified three dimensions: identification, affiliation, and exchange. Again, these overlap with Meyer and Allen's dimensions.

Since Meyer and Allen's dimensions encompass the others, this paper uses their framework for studying organizational commitment: affective, continuance, and normative commitment.

Research questions:

The study aims to investigate the interplay of attitude toward work and organizational commitment. It particularly answered the following questions:

1. What is the attitude of employees toward work in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive attitude and
 - 1.2. affective attitude ?

2. What is the organizational commitment of employees along with
 - 2.1. affective commitment,
 - 2.2. continuance commitment, and
 - 2.3. normative commitment ?

3. Is there a relationship between attitude toward work and organizational commitment?

Hypothesis

Human attitudes can shape how they behave towards specific things. Positive or negative attitudes can impact how someone acts towards those things. This study suggests that employees' attitudes towards their work can influence their commitment to the organization.

Scope and delimitation

The study limits its investigation to the attitude of employees toward work, specifically cognitive and affective attitude and organizational commitment along with affective, continuance and normative commitment. The population is limited to the employees of the institution.

Research methodology

The study is quantitative and uses a descriptive and correlational research design. It focuses on Divine Word College of Laoag and its employees. Questionnaires are used to collect data, and descriptive and inferential statistics, like weighted mean and Pearson r, are employed for analysis. Data collection involved sending a letter to the President for permission to distribute questionnaires, which were collected through employees' representatives. Ethical review was waived due to the research's lack of sensitive human issues.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Data presentation and analysis

The data are presented following the statement of the problems.

1. *What is the attitude of employees toward work in terms of:*
 - 1.1. *cognitive attitude and*
 - 1.2. *affective attitude*

Table 1: Attitude of employees toward work in terms of cognitive and affective attitude.

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>DI</i>
Cognitive attitude		
I know my work	4.06	High
I believe that I can perform my work easily	3.92	High
I have been in the work for quite some time	3.87	High
I am familiar with all the details of my work	3.89	High
I have the skills to carry out my work	3.91	High
I can carry out my work without the help of others	3.73	High
Composite Mean	3.90	High
Affective attitude		
I am happy with my work	3.87	High
I am always eager to show up for work	3.81	High

My work gives me satisfaction	3.84	High
I feel good because I can perform my work	3.88	High
My work is important to me	3.93	High
My work gives me a sense of meaning	3.97	High
Composite Mean	3.88	High
Overall Mean	3.98	High

Source: Rosenberg and Hovland (1960)

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree/Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree/High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree/Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree/Very Low

The data in the table shows that employees generally have a positive attitude towards work, with both cognitive and affective aspects rated as "agree/high" with an overall mean rating of 3.98. This indicates that their attitude towards work is high, neither very low nor moderate. Specifically, employees feel confident in their abilities and skills to perform their work independently, as they have gained experience over time. This high cognitive attitude towards work boosts their self-efficacy, according to Abun et al. (2021). Additionally, employees express happiness and satisfaction with their work, which motivates them to perform well and gives purpose to their lives. This positive affective attitude towards work also enhances employee performance, as noted by Abun et al. (2021).

2. What is the organizational commitment of employees along with:

- 2.1. affective commitment
- 2.2. continuance commitment
- 2.3. normative commitment

Table 2: Organizational Commitment.

Indicator	Mean	DI
Affective commitment		
I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organization	3.89	High
I feel as if this organization's problems are my own	3.75	High
I feel like 'part of my family at this organization	3.71	High
I feel 'emotionally attached to this organization	3.73	High
This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	3.88	High
I feel a strong sense of belonging to this organization	3.67	High
Composite Mean	3.77	High
Continuance commitment		
It would be very hard for me to leave my job at this organization right now even if I wanted to	3.74	High
Too much of my life would be disrupted if I left my organization	3.48	High
Right now, staying with my job at this organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire	3.64	High
I believe I have too few options to consider leaving this organization	3.63	High
One of the few negative consequences of leaving my job at this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives elsewhere.	3.56	High
One of the major reasons I continue to work for this organization is that leaving would require considerable personal sacrifice	3.69	High
Composite Mean	3.62	High
Normative commitment		
I must remain with my organization.	3.64	High
Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave.	3.50	High
I would feel guilty if I left this organization now	3.62	High
This organization deserves my loyalty	3.73	High
I would not leave my organization right now because of my sense of obligation to it	3.74	High
I owe a great deal to this organization.	3.84	High
Composite Mean	3.68	High

Overall Mean	3.69	High
---------------------	-------------	-------------

Source: Meyer and Allen (1997).

The data from the table reveals that overall, employees show a high level of organizational commitment, including affective, continuance, and normative commitment, with an overall mean rating of 3.69, interpreted as "agree/high". This suggests that their commitment is substantial, neither very low nor moderate. When examining each dimension separately, they all received similarly high mean ratings (3.77, 3.62, and 3.68).

Regarding affective commitment, employees feel emotionally connected to the institution, seeing it as part of their family and providing meaning to their lives (Sinaga et al., 2019). This emotional attachment leads to better observation and analysis of work-related issues.

Concerning continuance commitment, employees acknowledge that leaving the job would be difficult due to the disruption it would cause in their lives and the scarcity of opportunities elsewhere. They also feel obligated to stay with the institution, even if it may not be in their best interest, out of loyalty (Khan et al., 2016; Kasoge, 2019).

While affective and continuance commitment positively impact job performance and satisfaction, normative commitment does not (Igbomor & Ogbuma, 2024).

Problem 3. Is there a relationship between attitude toward work and organizational commitment?

Table 3: Correlation table

		Affective commitment	Continuance commitment	Normative commitment	Overall commitment
Cognitive attitude	Pearson Correlation	.416**	.351**	.041	.331**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.610	.000
Affective attitude	Pearson Correlation	.321**	.396**	.035	.312**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.658	.000
Overall attitude	Pearson Correlation	.393**	.400**	.041	.343**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.611	.000

**p<0.01

The table shows a significant positive relationship ($r=0.343$, $p<.01$) between attitude toward work and organizational commitment. This means that individuals with more positive work attitudes tend to have higher organizational commitment levels.

Breaking down work attitudes, both cognitive and affective dimensions correlate positively with certain aspects of organizational commitment. Cognitive attitude correlates positively with affective ($r=0.321$, $p<.01$) and continuance ($r=0.416$, $p<.01$) commitment. Similarly, affective attitude correlates positively with affective ($r=0.396$, $p<.01$) and continuance ($r=0.351$, $p<.01$) commitment.

However, the normative component of commitment doesn't show significant relationships with cognitive or affective attitudes toward work, nor with overall attitude. The correlation values for normative commitment range from 0.041 to 0.035, with p-values greater than .05. This suggests that individuals' sense of obligation to their organization may not strongly depend on their cognitive or affective work attitudes.

In summary, while cognitive and affective work attitudes are linked to affective and continuance commitment, the normative commitment seems somewhat independent. This underscores the multidimensional nature of organizational commitment and its relationship with work attitudes.

Result and Discussions

Organizational performance is linked to various factors within the workforce, not just salaries and benefits. Stackhouse et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of organizational commitment in this regard. Studies by Meyer et al. (1989) and Yousef (2000) have shown that employees' commitment significantly impacts organizational performance. This commitment is influenced not only by tangible rewards but also by employees' attitudes toward their work.

The current study highlights that employees' cognitive and affective attitudes toward their work affect their organizational commitment, particularly in terms of affective and continuance commitment. This means that when employees understand and enjoy their work, they are more likely to feel loyal to the organization and stay with it. Therefore, management faces the challenge of investing in training and development to enhance employees' skills and knowledge, while also providing the necessary resources and effective leadership to foster employees' enjoyment and satisfaction with their work.

Conclusion

The study investigated how employees' feelings about their work affect their commitment to the organization. It found that employees generally have positive attitudes toward their work, especially in terms of affective and cognitive aspects. Their commitment to the organization is also high. The correlation analysis revealed a significant link between employees' work attitudes and their commitment to the organization. This suggests that to strengthen organizational commitment, it's important to improve employees' attitudes toward their work, especially their cognitive and affective attitudes.

Authors' Contribution

Authors Contribution:

Conceptualization: EB.N. E.B.V. **Methodology:** E.B.N. E.B.V. **Data collection:** E.B.N **Formal Analysis:** ElB.N., E.B.V. **Writing-Review and Editing:** E.B.N., E.B. V.

All authors have read and agreed to the published final version of the manuscript

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study, due to the research does not deal with vulnerable groups or sensitive issues.

Data Availability Statement: the data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. Data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

Funding: the study is privately funded.

References

Abdalkrim, G.M. & Elhalim, T.A.A. (2016). Attitude toward work, job satisfaction, and job performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v6-i12/2547>

Abun, D., Ubaso, A.L.A., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Ranay, F.B. (2021). Attitude toward the work and its influence on the individual work performance of employees: Basis for Attitude Management. *Technium Social Science Journal*, 18, 378-394.

Ajayi, K.O. & Muraina, K.O. (2016). *Collective bargaining as a tool for industrial conflict in Organization and Conflict Resolution*. IGI Global: Publisher Timely Knowledge. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-9850-5.ch008>.

Ajzen, I. (1993). *New directions in attitude measurement*. Walter de Gruyter.

Akcay, R., Ulutas, M. & Sevinc, N. (2016). Attitudes towards work in educational institutions. *Journal of Human Sciences* 13(1),1072.

Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1990.tb00506.x>

Allport, G. W. (1935). *Attitudes, a handbook of social psychology* (Murchison, C., Ed.). Clark University Press.

Almeida, A., Faisca, L. & de Jesus, S.N. (2012). Positive attitudes at work, some of its consequents and antecedents: a study with hotel professional. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 1(6), 71-82.

Angle, H. L., & Perry, J. L. (1981). An empirical assessment of organizational commitment and organizational effectiveness. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 26(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392596>

Aries, S. & Rizqi, M. (2013). Employee's Job Performance: The effect of attitude toward work, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. *Jurnal Teknik Industri*, 15(1), 13-24.

Balfour, D. L., & Wechsler, B. (1996). Organizational commitment: Antecedents and outcomes in public organizations. *Public Productivity & Management Review*, 19(3), 256–277. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3380574>

Baysal, A.C. & Tekarslan, E. (1996). *İşletmeciler için davranış bilimleri*. Avcıol

Becker, T. E., Billings, R. S., Eveleth, D. M., & Gilbert, N. L. (1996). Foci and bases of employee commitment: implications for job performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39, 464–482. <https://doi.org/10.2307/256788>

Becker, H.S. (1960). Notes on the concept of commitment. *American Journal of Sociology*, 66, 32-42. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/222820>

Best, P.W. (1994). *Locus of control, personal commitment and commitment to the organization*. Unpublished Master Communication thesis. University of South Africa, Pretoria

Borst, R. T., Kruyen, P. M., Lako, C. J., & de Vries, M. S. (2020). The attitudinal, behavioural, and performance outcomes of work engagement: A comparative meta-analysis across the public, semipublic, and private sector. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 40(4), 613–640. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734371X19840399>

Brayfield, A. H., & Crockett, W. H. (1955). Employee attitudes and employee performance. *Psychological Bulletin*, 52(5), 396–424. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0045899>

Cabrera, W., & Estacio, D. (2022). Job attitude as a factor on employees' performance. *International Journal of Economics Development Research (IJEDR)*, 3(1), 13–35. <https://doi.org/10.37385/ijedr.v3i1.254>

Cambridge Dictionary (n.d). *Age*. Retrieved May 3, 2024 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/>

Cascio, W. F. (2006). The economic impact of employee behaviours on organizational performance. *California Management Review*, 48(4), 41-59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000812560604800401>

Ceylan, C. (2020). *Management by values in educational organizations: A case study of a technical university*. IGI Global: Publisher Timely Knowledge. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-2562-3.ch005>

Cherry, K. (2021). *Attitudes and behaviour in psychology*. Very Well Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com>

Dewey, J. (1922). *Human nature and conduct: An introduction to social psychology*. Henry Holt.

Fischer, R., & Mansell, A. (2009). Commitment across cultures: A meta-analytic approach. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 40 (8), 1339-1358. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/27752450>. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jibs.2009.14>

Greenberg, J. and Baron, R.A. (2008). *Behavior in organizations*. Pearson, Hoboken, 269-274.

Herrera, J. & Heras-Rosas, C. (2021). The organizational commitment in the company and Its relationship with the psychological contract. *Frontier in Psychology*, 11, 609211. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.609211>

Idrees H, Hynek J, Xu J, Akbar A and Jabeen S (2022) Impact of knowledge management capabilities on new product development performance through the mediating role of organizational agility and moderating role of business model innovation. *Frontier in Psychology*, 13, 950054. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.950054>

Idris, A. M., & Manganaro, M. (2017). Relationships between psychological capital, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment in the Saudi oil and petrochemical industries. *Journal of Human Behaviour in the Social Environment*, 27, 251–269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2017.1279098>.

Igbomor, E. & Ogbuma, S.M. (2024). Empirical evidence of the effect of organizational commitment on employee job performance. *International Journal of Research and Publication*, 5(1), 1941-1947.

Johnson, R.E. & Chang, C.H. (2006). “I” is to continuance as “we” are too affective: The relevance of the self-concepts for organizational commitment. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27, 549-570. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.364>

Kasogela, O.K. (2019). The impact of continuance commitment on job performance. *Advance Journal of Social Science*, 5(1).

Khan, R., Naseem, A. & Masood, S.A. (2016). Effect of continuance commitment and organizational cynicism on employee’s satisfaction in engineering organization. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 7(4).

Koffka, K. (1935). *Principles of Gestalt psychology*. Harcourt, Brace, and Co.

Lee, H., Cha, S. & Park, H. The effect of technology-exploration on product innovation: an analysis based on Korean manufacturing SMEs. *International Journal of Quality Innovation*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40887-016-0009-y>

- Leonard, A.C. (2009). *Alignment with sound relationships and SLA support*. Encyclopedia of Information Science and Technology, Second Edition. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-60566-026-4>.
- Liska, A. E. (1974). The impact of attitude on behaviour: attitude-social support interaction. *Pacific Sociological Review*, 17(1), 83-97.
- Lowry R. J. (1973). *AH Maslow: An intellectual portrait*. Brooks/Cole
- Macneil, I.R. (1985). Relational contract: What we do and do not know. *Wisconsin Law Review* 1, 483-52
- Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D. M. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedent's correlation, and consequences of organizational commitment. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108, 171-194. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.108.2.171>
- Menon, A.S. & Priyadarshini, R.G., (2018). A study on the effect of workplace negativity factors on employee engagement mediated by emotional exhaustion. *The 3rd International Conference on Materials and Manufacturing Engineering 2018*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/390/1/012027>
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1984). Testing the 'side-bet theory' of organizational commitment: some methodological considerations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 69, 372–378. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.69.3.372>
- Meyer, J. P., Paunonen, S. V., Gellatly, I. R., Goffin, R. D., & Jackson, D. N. (1989). Organizational commitment and job performance: It's the nature of the commitment that counts. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(1), 152–156. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.74.1.152>
- Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
- Meyer, J.P., Allen, N.J. & Gellatly, I.R. (1990). Affective and continuance commitment to the organization: Evaluation of measures and analysis of concurrent and time-lagged relations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 75, 710–720. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.75.6.710>
- Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace. Theory, research and application*. Sage
- Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D. J., Herscovitch, L., & Topolnytsky, L. (2002). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the agency: A meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61(1), 20-52. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1842>
- Meyer, J. P., Becker, T. E., & Vandenberghe, C. (2004). Employee commitment and motivation: a conceptual analysis and integrative model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89, 991–1007. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.89.6.991>
- Miller, K. (2003). *Values, attitudes and job satisfaction* In Robbins, S.P., Odendaal A. & Roodt, G. (eds). *Organizational behaviour: Global and Southern African perspectives*. Pearson Education South Africa
- Miller, D. & Lee, J. (2001). The people make the process: commitment to employees, decision making and performance. *Journal of Management*, 27, 163–189. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063\(00\)00094-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063(00)00094-5)
- Morrow, P.C. (1993). *The theory and measurement of work commitment*. Jai.

Muhammad, S., Afridi, F. K., Ali, M. W., Shah, W. U., & Alasan, I. I. (2021). Effect of training on employee commitment: mediating role of job satisfaction. *Pakistan Journal of Society, Education and Language (PJSEL)*, 7(1), 28-37.

Myers, D. (2013). *Social Psychology*. McGraw-Hills

Önal, S. E. (2015). *Kamu çalışanlarının verimliliğinde işe yönelik tutumlar, örgütsel adalet algısı ve algılanan sosyal desteğin önemi, kalkınmada anahtar verimlilik dergisi, sayı:290*. T.C.Bilim, sanayi ve Teknoloji Bakanlığı.

Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace. Theory, research and application*. Sage

O'Reilly, C. (1989). Corporations, culture and commitment. *California Management Review*, 31, 9–24.

O'Reilly, C. A., & Chatman, J. (1986). Organizational commitment and psychological attachment: The effects of compliance, identification, and internalization on prosocial behaviour. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71, 492-499. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.492>

Ortmeyer, D. (1949). The Concept of Attitude. *Proceedings of the Iowa Academy of Science*, 56(1), 279-284.

Perloff R.M. (2013). *The dynamics of persuasion: Communication and attitudes in the 21st century*. Routledge

Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603–609. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0037335>

Porter, L. W., & Lawer, E. E. (1965). *Managerial attitudes and performance*. Homewood.

Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603–609. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0037335>

Reicher, A.E. (1985). A review and reconceptualization of organizational commitment. *Academy of Management Review*, 10, 465–476. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258128>

Rahiman, H. & Kodikal, R. (2017). Impact of employee work-related attitudes on job performance. *British Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 13(2).

Rousseau, D. (1995). *Psychological contracts in organizations. Understanding written and unwritten agreements*. Sage.

Sinaga, A.T.I., Lumbanraja, P., Sadalia, I. & Silalahi, A.S. (2019). *The influence of affective commitment on the employees' innovative work behaviour*. SciTePress-Science and Technology Publications.

Solinger, O. N., van Olffen, W., & Roe, R. A. (2008). Beyond the three-component model of organizational commitment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(1), 70-83

Stackhouse, L.E., Zaman, F.M. & Turner, W. (2022). Effect of employee commitment on organizational performance; Case of textile firms in Sweden. *Journal of Human Resource & Leadership*, 6 (2), 6(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.53819/81018102t5074>

Thurstone, L. L. (1929). *The Measurement of Attitude*. University of Chicago Press

Titchener, E. B. (1910). *A textbook of psychology*. Macmillan Company.

Youssef, C.M. & Luthans, F. (2007). Positive organizational behaviour in the workplace: The impact of hope, optimism, and resilience. *Journal of Management*, 33 (5), 774-800. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206307305562>

Yousef, D.A. (2000). Organizational commitment: a mediator of the relationships of leadership behaviour with job satisfaction and performance in a non-western country. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 15(1), 6-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940010305270>

Publisher's Note: DWIJMH stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

© 2024 by the authors. Licensee DWIJMH. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Divine Word International Journal of Management and Humanities. DWIJMH is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.